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The event aims to discuss contemporary research across various scientific fields, exchange new scientific ideas, and support scientific activities aligned with global innovative processes.

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The main objective of this International Scientific-Practical Conference is to consolidate the results of contemporary research across various scientific fields and strengthen the integration of science and practice through advanced scientific approaches.

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3. **Каримова А.С., Аскарлова Р.И., Имомова Ё.М.** Изучение полифенолов растительного сбора из малины обыкновенной и ежевики сизой // *Universum: химия и биология.* — 2025. — 128 с.
4. **Бобрышева Т.Н., Анисимова Г.С., Золоторёва М.С.** Полифенолы как перспективные биологически активные соединения. — **Российский национальный исследовательский медицинский университет имени Н.И. Пирогова**, Министерство здравоохранения Российской Федерации. — Москва, Российская Федерация.
5. **Лукин А.А.** Методы определения полифенолов в пищевых системах. — **ФГАОУ ВО Южно-Уральский государственный университет (НИУ)**. — Челябинск, Россия.
6. **Kosimova Z.T.** Organizmdagi oksidlanish stress holatida polifenollarning roli // *II Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari.*

**UCH MARKAZLI O‘RAMA EGRI CHIZIQNI
TO‘G‘IRLASH VA HAQIQIY UZUNLIGINI ANIQLASH.**

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***Anotatsiya:** Ushbu maqolada bir tekislikda yotuvchi egri chiziqlarni to‘g‘irlash masalalari ko‘rib chiqiladi. Egri chiziqni to‘g‘irlash uchun markazlari O_1, O_2 va O_3 bo‘lgan aylana yo‘ylaridan iborat uch markazli o‘rama qurilgan. O‘rama to‘rtta aylana yoyidan tashkil topgan. O‘ramani to‘g‘irlash jarayonida har bir yoyning uzunligini aniqlash zarur bo‘lgan. Mazkur jarayonda kichik xordalar*

(kesmalar) usulidan foydalanilgan. Ushbu usulning mohiyati shundan iboratki, to'g'rilanayotgan tekis egri chiziqqa uning kichik xordalaridan iborat siniq chiziq ichki chizib boriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Egri chiziq, uch markazli o'rama, aylana yoyi, tekislik, trayektoriya, uzluksiz harakat, markaz.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются вопросы спрямления плоских кривых линий, лежащих в одной плоскости. Для спрямления кривой построена трёхцентровая спираль, состоящая из дуг окружностей с центрами O_1 , O_2 и O_3 . Спираль состоит из четырёх дуг окружности. Для её спрямления необходимо определить длину каждой дуги. В работе применён метод малых хорд, суть которого заключается в том, что в спрямляемую плоскую кривую вписывается ломаная линия, звенья которой представляют собой малые хорды данной кривой.

Ключевые слова: Кривая линия, трёхцентровая спираль, дуга окружности, плоскость, траектория, непрерывное движение, центр.

Abstract: This article examines the problem of rectifying plane curves lying in a single plane. To perform the rectification, a three-centered spiral curve composed of circular arcs with centers O_1 , O_2 and O_3 is constructed. The spiral consists of four circular arcs. To straighten the spiral, the length of each arc must be determined. The author applies the method of small chords, which is based on inscribing a broken (polygonal) line into the given plane curve, where each segment represents a small chord of the curve.

Keywords: Curve, three-centered spiral, circular arc, plane, trajectory, continuous motion, center.

Kirish: Chizma geometriya va muhandislik grafikasi fanlarida egri chiziqlarni tahlil qilish muhim nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega. Egri chiziqlar mashinasozlik, qurilish, arxitektura, mexanika va texnika sohalarida keng qo'llaniladi. Ayniqsa, turli shakldagi prujinalar, spiral elementlar, quvurlar, vint mexanizmlar va aylanuvchi detallarni loyihalashda egri chiziqlarning geometrik xossalarini chuqur o'rganish talab etiladi.

Egri chiziqlarni to‘g‘irlash masalasi ularning haqiqiy uzunligini aniqlash bilan chambarchas bog‘liq bo‘lib, bu masala ko‘plab muhandislik hisob-kitoblarida uchraydi. Chunki ko‘pincha egri chiziqning analitik tenglamasi berilmagan bo‘lib, u geometrik qurilishlar asosida hosil qilinadi. Bunday hollarda egri chiziq uzunligini aniqlash murakkablashadi va maxsus geometrik usullardan foydalanishni talab etadi.

Mazkur maqolada tekis egri chiziqlarning bir turi bo‘lgan uch markazli o‘rama egri chiziqni to‘g‘irlash masalasi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Ushbu turdagi o‘ramalar texnikada keng qo‘llanilishi bilan birga, geometrik jihatdan murakkab tuzilishga ega bo‘lgani sababli ularning haqiqiy uzunligini aniqlash dolzarb masalalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Asosiy qismni: O‘rama xar hil uzunlikdagi radiuslar bilan chizilgan aylana yoylaridan tuzilgan ochiq va ravon egri chiziqdir. O‘ramalarni bitta markaz, shuningdek bir necha markazlar yordamida yasash mumkin. Texnikada, ko‘pincha ko‘p markazli o‘ramalar ishlatiladi.

Bizning misolda uch markazli o‘ramani yasash 1-shaklga tasvirlangan. Uch markazli o‘ramaning markazlari qilib teng tomonli uchburchakning, masalan, tanlab olingan O_1 , O_2 va O_3 uchlari olingan. So‘ng bu uchburchakning O_1 uchidan $R = O_1$, $O_3 = 15\text{mm}$ radius bilan yoy chizib, bu yoyning O_2 va O_1 tomonining davomi bilan kesishgan A nuqtasi aniqlanadi. Shundan keyin O_2 markazdan $R = 30$ radius bilan ikkinchi yoy chizilib, uning O_3 , O_2 tomonning davomi bilan kesishib B nuqtasi topiladi. Keyin O_3 markazdan $R = 45$ radius bilan uchinchi yoy chizilib, bu yoyning O_1 , O_3 tomonining davomi bilan kesishib C nuqtasi topiladi. Yana O_1 markazdan $R = 60$ radius bilan to‘rtinchi yoy chizilib D nuqta aniqlanadi va hokazo. Natijada izlanayotgan uch markazli $ABCD$ o‘rama hosil bo‘ladi (1-rasm).

Uch markazli o‘rama egri chiziqni to‘g‘irlash uchun $O_3 A$, AB , BC va CD yoylarning uzunliklarini quyidag I formuladan foydalanamiz.

$$KL = \frac{2\pi r}{n}; \quad O_1 \quad O_2 \quad O_3 \quad R \quad A \quad B \quad C \quad D \quad K \quad L \quad n \quad m$$

Bu yerda;

KL - sektor yoy uzunligi

$O_3 A$ - o'rama sektor uzunligi ,

π – o'zgarmas son,

R - sektor yoy radiusi,

n - sektorlar soni.

$$1) O_3 A = \frac{2\pi r}{3} = \frac{2 \times 3,14 \times 15}{3} = \frac{94,2}{3} = 31,4 \text{ mm}$$

$$2) AB = \frac{2\pi r}{3} = \frac{2 \times 3,14 \times 30}{3} = \frac{188,4}{3} = 62,8 \text{ mm}$$

$$3) BC = \frac{2\pi r}{3} = \frac{2 \times 3,14 \times 45}{3} = \frac{282,6}{3} = 94,2 \text{ mm}$$

$$3) CD = \frac{2\pi r}{3} = \frac{2 \times 3,14 \times 60}{3} = \frac{376,8}{3} = 125,6 \text{ mm}$$

Boshlang'ich radiusi R 15 mm bo'lgan urinma egri chiziq yoylarini ketma-ket o'lchab tog'ri chiziqqa qo'yilganda: $L = O_3 A + AB + BC + CD = 31,4 + 62,8 = 94,2 + 125,6 = 314$ mm ga teng bo'ldi. Hosil bo'lgan hamma yoylarning yig'indisi, egri chiziqni to'g'rilanganligi deyiladi.

1-rasm

Xulosa: Mazkur maqolada uch markazli o'rama egri chiziqni to'g'irlash va uning haqiqiy uzunligini aniqlash masalasi ko'rib chiqildi. O'rama geometrik qurilish asosida hosil qilinib, uning har bir yoyining uzunligi kichik xordalar

(kesmalar) usuli yordamida aniqlandi. Natijada egri chiziqning to'g'rilangan uzunligi hisoblab topildi.

Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, kichik xordalar (kesmalar) usuli ko'p markazli egri chiziqlarni tahlil qilishda samarali va ishonchli usul hisoblanadi. Ushbu usuldan foydalanish texnika va muhandislik amaliyotida, xususan, o'rama prujinalar, spiral elementlar va murakkab shaklli detallarni loyihalashda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Kelgusida ushbu tadqiqot natijalari asosida ko'p markazli o'ramalarning boshqa turlari uchun ham umumlashtirilgan hisoblash usullarini ishlab chiqish mumkin.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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